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Recommending Candidates to Recruitment System based on Machine Learning Paradigm

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Abstract

The Internet-based recruiting platforms become a primary recruitment channel in most companies. In this work, a learning model is proposed which work as Web Based Recruiting framework for the Web Based Recruiting sites enriched with features of ranking the candidates according to the relevance correspond to the requirement of recruiting sites. It contributes an intelligent system by employing machine learning algorithms to solve the candidate ranking problem and performing semantic matching techniques. It uses XML for guaranteeing a light, versatile, and standard mechanism for information representation, storing, and exchange. In the proposed model information regarding the candidates will be provided as an input. According to the inputs provided the list of ranked candidates will be suggested to the recruiting site using machine learning algorithm.

Keywords: Data Mining, Machine Learning, Recommender System, Text Mining, Web based recruiting.

1. Introduction

The tremendous growth of the World Wide Web (WWW) and the Electronic Commerce (E-Commerce) has changed the way of business in the field of human resources management. Nowadays, they offer many services like job posting, job searching, resume posting, candidate searching, some useful contents for job seekers and employers via the Internet. In addition to the rapid growth of web as a recruiting tool in recent years

demonstrating the success of employing Internet technology to the recruitment industry, they provide the process of attracting individuals on prompt timely basis, in sufficient numbers, and with appropriate qualifications, and easily encouraging them to apply for jobs with an organization at lower cost. Consequently, many job boards and Internet recruiting sites have been very active and tried to provide and develop new services to their customers. The traditional recruitment procedure consumes too much time and efforts to complete from job opening to getting the right candidates. Moreover the recruiting sites based on Web, have taken place the employment agencies on the global market. Therefore, the benefit of adopting the internet technology to the recruitment services industry is substantial. The hiring companies can open the job positions immediately and can directly search for the candidates with their preference criteria. For this purpose, Data mining [1] can be used as analytical tools for analyzing data. Moreover, Text mining, sometimes alternately referred to as text data mining, roughly equivalent to text analytics refers to the process of deriving high-quality information from text [2].

The web based recruiting service has expanded services in terms of useful contents to attract people, robot or agent services which are also used to assist job seekers in periodically search jobs with their predefined criteria and email them the results. Some processes of the web based recruiting service are not automated, for example, when recruiter posts the job to the sites, the sites staffs have to re-enter data into the system. It takes time from getting the job ads until posting to the web. In addition, there is no standard format for job posting and resume, the formats are different from site to site. Hence, the recruiter has to post the job differently at different sites and the job seeker has to post resume in different format. The proposed system may come up with these problems, because XML technology [3] can manage the semi-structured data in the document. Some approaches existing on XML related human resources management can be extended to the standard for job posting and resume posting services.

The main objectives can be listed as follows:

- 1) To find the most relevance candidates for the job posted by recruiting site.
- 2) After finding the relevance candidates, the results will be ranked with some threshold value K , top K candidates would be appointed to the company for further processing.

2. Related Works

Though DL approaches have proven the undertaking in different areas like Optimizers [4], Adversarial Attacks [5], Image Steganography [6], Intrusion Detection [7], Medical Images [8], [9]. Content based system deal with product features and user profiles and their matching. It first take into account the product/item features or profile and after that it matches it with that of the user profile, taste or user requirement for the particular item or product. Based on the similarity index the item that most satisfies the user need is recommended on the top [10]. Collaborative based system focus on item-item similarity or user-user similarity. It calculated the similarity either between the items or between the user's profiles. It then looks for the user tastes. Then either it makes the recommendation on the basis of item-item similarity score i.e. if the user like a particular item then he might also like the item that are similar to that item [11]. Knowledge based system attempts to suggest objects on inference about user's needs and preferences. This approach assists user in determination of suitable solutions from complex product and services assortments. In knowledge based system there is no need to gather information about a particular user because its judgments are independent of

individual taste [12]. Demographic system aim to find the user’s personal attribute through interactive dialog or other methods and then recommend the items [13]. Almost all recommender system have challenges and to get better performance and overcome these challenges, these approaches have been combined forming a new approach i.e. hybrid approach [14]. Authors Mourad Ykhlef, Shaha T. Al-Otaibi [15], have implemented the three techniques (Cosine similarity, Euclidean distance and New Jaccard measure), for ranking the candidates for the job postings. In [15], Diaby Mamadou et al. described a model that extracts the profile of the users from the social network, (facebook, LinkedIn), and recommend the job based on the three classes of documents, job offers, job categories and social network user profiles. Evaluates job applicants in online recruitment systems, using machine learning algorithms to solve the candidate ranking problem [16]. Domenico Ursino et al. [17], has proposed a model that is enriched with the features of taking profiles of users, and the data is represented in XML so that the intelligent model can recommend the relevance candidate. Gediminas Adomavicius and Alexander Tuzhilin in [18] have defined TF-IDF vector for document representation and cosine similarity for semantic matching between documents. In [19], authors Deppali et. al., have used matching methods like semantic matching, tree based matching and query matching for matching profile of applicants with hob recruiter.

3. Methodology

The proposed model is expected to provide a suitable candidate to recruitment system according to the requirement they have placed. Here the requirement of recruiter is extract from web accordingly the information regarding the competent candidate will be gathered. The conceptual model of a proposed system is shown in Figure 1. Different steps followed includes Job Offer

Figure 1. Conceptual model of proposed model for recommending candidates to recruiter.

Extraction (Web Crawler, Parsing), Document Preprocessing (Tokenization, Stop Word Removal, Synonym Expansion, Cosine Similarity Algorithm), Data Acquisition, Feature Selection (Features of Candidate Data, Features of Recruiter Data, Domain Knowledge), Document Representation, Semantic Matching and Ranking.

3.1. Dataset

As the research work required job related resumes of the candidates to be in place, an interface for candidate is developed through which they can provide their information. A module that extract the information regarding a vacancy on the web is developed. The research oriented relevant information regarding the candidate was studied and extracted. Also the jobs related information was extracted from the various recruitment sites available online.

3.2. Data Sets for Candidates

For testing the model, records of 250 candidates are taken, among the records of 10 candidates were taken as references as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Data Set for Candidate.

S.	Name	Address	Age	Gender	Marita	Qualification	Experience	Skill	Maior
1	Puja	Nepalgunj	25	Female	Single	BEIT	5	C,C++,Java	Java
2	Prasansa	Biratnagar	27	Female	Single	BSCCSIT	8	MYSQL,SQL	SQL
3	Suraj	Jhapa	35	Male	Married	MEcomputer	15	C,C++,Java	C
4	Diggag	Lalitpur	25	Male	Single	BSCCSIT	3	CCNA,linux	CCNA
5	Suraj	Kathmandu	20	Male	Single	BEIT	2	C#, .NET	.NET
6	Raju	Kathmandu	36	Male	Married	MEComputer	16	C,C++,Java	c++
7	Dhurba	Nuwakot	32	Male	Married	MSCCSIT	10	oracel,SQL	SQL
8	Lok	Kathmandu	37	Male	Married	MEcomputer	13	PHP,Agile	PHP
9	Rashmi	Lalitpur	29	Female	Single	BSCCSIT	6	python	Python
10	Rahul	Kathmandu	24	Male	Single	BEIT	5	c#, .NET	c#

Table 2. Relevant Candidates for Experiment 8

S.No	Name	Address	Age	Marital	Gender	Qualification	Grade	Experience	Skill	E-Mail
1	Sudip	Lalitpur	35	Married	Male	MCA	90	12	PHP	thapasudip@yahoo.com
2	Sujan	Lalitpur	50	Married	Male	MCA	87	21	PHP,CSS	prajapatisuju@hotmail.com

Table 3. Ranked Candidates

S.N	Name	Addres	Ag	Marital	Gende	Qualificatio	Grad	Experienc	Skill	E-Mail
1	Sujan	Lalitpu	50	Marrie	Male	MCA	87	21	PHP,CS	prajapatisuju@hotmail.co
2	Sudip	Lalitpu	35	Marrie	Male	MCA	90	12	PHP	thapasudip@yahoo.com

3.3. Document Processing

When the job offer with their links are extracted by crawler, it is further preprocessed for text mining using document preprocessing techniques.

1) *Tokenization*: Tokenization is accomplished by using space to split the sequence of tokens. But, some special token like url, email id are also regarded as single token.

2) *Stop Word Removal*: The stop word such as a, an, the, and prepositions is created and the tokens contained in the stop word list are discarded.

3) *Synonym Expansion*: Synonym Expansion was carried out by searching each token in the dictionary and

transforming each word to the base word. For example in this research, different terminologies like C#, Dot Net, ASP, and ASP.Net are semantically similar.

4) *Cosine Similarity Algorithm*: Cosine similarity is a measure of similarity between two vectors by measuring the cosine of the angle between them. The cosine of 0 is 1, and less than 1 for any other angle. The cosine of the angle between two vectors thus determines whether two vectors are pointing in roughly the same direction. In data mining we can use this technique to find the similarity of the documents. For documents d_1 and d_2 ,

$$\text{Cos}(d_1, d_2) = \frac{d_1 \cdot d_2}{\|d_1\| * \|d_2\|} \quad (1)$$

where, dot (.) indicates the vector dot product and $\|d\|$ is the length of vector.

Similarly, recruiters are also represented in a vector.

5) *Semantic Matching and Ranking*: cosine similarity module is used to find the semantic matching between the candidates and recruiters' requirements. Rather than comparing the exact match, the concept hierarchy is used for matching. As instance, company who needed the candidate with 3 years' experience also like to hire candidates with more than 3 years' experience. For ranking purpose, among 'N' relevance candidates 'N/2' are displayed on the basis or priority. Priority is assigned on the basis of academic qualification and years of experiences.

4. Experiment Setup

Experimental results of the steps were carried out for gathering the information from web using web crawler, XML pattern to define an applicant, XML pattern to define recruiter, XML parser to handle the data regarding recruiter and a module to extract information from the recruiter's site. Using C#.NET, XML Pattern was used to define an applicant and recruiter. Further, modules to extract the information from the recruiter sites and to create the vector representations of candidate was defined. Data were extracted from the following websites.

- 1) <http://www.jobsnepal.com>
- 2) <http://www.jagire.com>
- 3) <http://www.merjob.com>
- 4) <http://www.deerwalk.com/careers>
- 5) <https://career.lftechnology.com/>

5. Result

Different 11 experiments were performed. Among them, for Experiment 8, Intel Communication PVT.LTD located in Lalitpur, Nepal needed "PHP Programmer Fresher" having 2 years' experience with graduate certificate. The suggested model suggested the candidates as shown in Table 2.

Half the top candidates are displayed from relevance candidates is shown in Table 3. The result show that candidate having both the knowledge of CSS and PHP is ranked first while the candidate was in second position earlier.

5.1. Result Validation

In order to validate the recommendation approach, we conducted a multi-step experiment with a group of 50 candidates. The participants in the experiment were randomly taken as input data and the vacant post of the recruiter is taken from the web. The experiment was separated into two different phases. In a first step, candidates were asked to provide their profiles. We therefore implemented a web interface by which we were able to capture candidate's data in a structured digital format. The data gathering was organized in a similar way to the registration procedures of many online job-portals.

The following data was collected and used as the input data for candidate recommender.

- 1) Demographic Data (eg DOB, Contact information)
- 2) Educational Data
- 3) Job Experiences
- 4) Language Skill

5.2. Research Validation

In order to evaluate the quality of the recommendations generated by the system, we considered the list of recommendations as a list of top n items. In our case these items either are the top 'N' candidates that best fit the job in consideration. The result list is based on calculated predictions based on candidate profile. Authors in [20], have used the following mathematical model to define the diversity of a top 'N' list of recommendations as the average of their pair wise dissimilarities.

- 1) In Experiment number 1 we get, Diversity = 0.06
- 2) In Experiment number 2 we get, Diversity= 0.03
- 3) In Experiment number 3 we get, Diversity= 0.0361
- 4) In Experiment number 4 we get, Diversity= 0.1261
- 5) In Experiment number 5 we get, Diversity= 0.13512
- 6) In Experiment number 6 we get, Diversity= 0.0
- 7) In Experiment number 7 we get, Diversity= 0.0
- 8) In Experiment number 8 we get, Diversity= 0.03513
- 9) In Experiment number 9 we get, Diversity= 0.02133
- 10) In Experiment number 10 we get, Diversity= 0.0033
- 11) In Experiment number 11 we get, Diversity= 0.0000033

6. Conclusion and Future Directions

In this research, a model was designed to recommend the most relevance candidates to the recruiter using machine learning paradigms. It along with increasing the prediction accuracy also help to solve the problem of providing direction to the recruiter by providing better personnel selection. Tracking the present preferences of the recruiter regarding the suitable candidate, helps to prioritize only the relevant candidate as against the irrelevant candidates that are shortlisted after the content based matching of the candidate. The proposed model has given the ranked result within the time complexity of $O(mn)$ where m is the number of candidates and n is the number of recruiter.

To continue further, Candidates can be sorted according to their geographical location. If same candidate